

Pradeep Maurya*

Dr. Anamika Gulati**

Comparative Study of Covaxin, Covishield, Sputnik-V, and Corbevax

Introduction

On 22 march 2020, India decided to lock down travel and transport due to the increased covid-19 case. (*Restricted Use of COVAXIN Under Clinical Trial Mode*, 2021) Indian scientists started the discovery of medicine for these sudden calamities. They collaborated with Chinese, European, and American scientists for gene sequencing. Gene sequencing is the essential step for the development of any vaccine (Khan & Dhama, 2021, 2). After a great effort, India developed its indigenous vaccine amid this covid-19 outburst. ICMR, with the collaboration of Bharat Biotech, developed covid-19 vaccine "Covaxin." The government of India facilitated a smooth pathway of licensing, clearance, regulatory norms, and collaboration with other agencies. The clinical trial was done with the AIIMS Patna.

Hypothesis

Covaxin is a promising vaccine, compared to Covishield, Sputnik-V, Corbevax, and Covovax.

Objective

- 1- To study the efficacy of the Covid 19 vaccine.
- 2- To study the accessibility of covid vaccine.
- 3- To study the storage condition of the vaccine.
- 4- To study the cost of the vaccine
- 5- To study the mode of administration of a vaccine
- 6- To study the age covering capacity of the

vaccine.

- 7- To study the Multipole analysis of vaccines.

Research Question

- 1- Is the efficacy of Covaxin greater than Covishield, SputnikV, Corbex, and Covobax?
- 2- Which is the suitable vaccine for vaccination based on efficacy, assessability, storage condition, cost, mode of administration, and age coverage?
- 3- How to use Multipole software for analyzing issues of policy?

Methodology

Determination of quality and efficacy of vaccine depends on the parameters taken for the assessment. The qualitative analysis discusses the efficacy and usefulness of the vaccine. Qualitative analysis ensures the curative capacity of the medicine. Quantitative observation expresses its strength. This study includes secondary data. Data is taken from various institutions. Bharat Biotech International ltd and the Indian council of medical research (ICMR) provide the Covaxin-related information. This information is taken for the study and observation of the functioning of the vaccine. Information is gathered by a secondary source in the place of a primary source. Data on vaccine efficacy, cost, accessibility, storage condition, and age coverage area are collected from the trial conducting institutes. Descriptive discussion is based on the multipole analysis.

Literature Review-

The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare issued a document permitting restricted use of Covaxin on 11th January 2021. This was the 4th version of the critical and scientific review. This version confirmed the vaccination from a broader perspective. According to these documents, clinical trials are bound by the Declaration of Helsinki. This document details the use, safety, precaution, and complications of the vaccine. Covaxin is firstly developed for older people (more than 50 years).

Discussion

The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare encouraged ICMR and Bharat Biotech International Limited to develop the vaccine for Covid-19. ICMR, in collaboration with Medical Research Centers in other countries, did genome sequencing of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Genome sequencing helped to understand the DNA structure of the virus and helped in developing a rapid vaccine. The Covid-19 virus is a variant of the SARS virus. The Union Health Ministry, in a notification issued on 11th January 2021, gave detailed information on Covaxin developed by ICMR and Bharat Biotech. The name of this document is- **“Restricted Use of COVAXIN™ Under Clinical Trial Mode Implementation Plan No: BBIL/COVAXIN™/2021 Version No: 4.0; Date: 11-01-2021.”** Permission given by CDSCO/DCGI has also been included in this document.

The Central Ethics Committee on Human Research (CECHR) found that there was no unethical practice in the development of Covaxin.

Different variants of Coronavirus burst in different parts of the world. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) broke out with a 35% mortality rate in the Middle East region. Porcine epidemic diarrhea coronavirus (PEDV) in the US. (*Restricted Use of COVAXIN Under Clinical Trial Mode, 2021*)

Coronavirus is a positive-stranded RNA-type virus. Its genome is the longest (27 to 32 kb) among RNA-type viruses. This genome is surrounded by an envelope made up of nucleocapsid proteins. Three

structural proteins are associated with the envelope of the SARS-CoV virus 1. Membrane protein, 2. Envelope protein, and 3. Spike protein. Spike protein mediates the virus to enter the host cell. SARS-CoV-2 transmits from one person to another person through respiratory droplets. This virus starts replicating by attaching to the epithelial cell of the upper respiratory tract of the host individual. The initial propagation of the virus does not show an immune response. Then the virus propagates and migrates down the respiratory tract and begins showing a more robust innate immune response. (Das, 2022, 289) The RT-PCR test is helpful in knowing the viral load, infectivity, and clinical course of SARS-CoV-2. (Paradkar, 2022) Nasal swabs and sputum are an early marker of the innate immune response and express virus yield in the tract. Symptoms of SARS-CoV-2 infection show after about five days of the incubation period. In contrast, the symptoms of death of a person can be from 6 to 41 days. The most common symptoms of SARS-CoV-2 are fever, cough, fatigue, sputum production, headache, hemoptysis, diarrhea, dyspnea, and lymphopenia. (Thuluva & Gunner, 2022, 9)

A premier institute of ICMR National Institute of Virology (NIV) in a partnership of Bharat Biotech International Limited has developed an indigenous virion inactivated SARS CoV-2 virus vaccine (COVAXIN™) The non-clinical study to ensuring the safety of the COVAXIN™ was performed in the compliance with the norms of Good Laboratory Practice (GLP). Three animal models Mice, Rats, and Rabbits were used to evaluate the immunogenicity and safety of the COVAXIN™ vaccine and it was found to be safe and immunogenic in all the animal models. The efficacy of this vaccine has been evaluated in Rhesus macaque and Syrian Hamsters by challenging vaccinated macaques with wild type virus. Two dose vaccination regimens were included in the study of immunogenicity, safety and efficacy of this vaccine. A total 375 participants participated in phase 1 trial and generated safety data without reactogenicity. Covaxin™ induced binding and neutralizing antibody response. 380 participants of

the age between 12 to 65 years participated in the 2nd phase of the trial. No immunogenicity was seen in any participants.

The Covaxin has been approved by DCGI on 03/01/2021, with the permission number MF/BIO/21/000002 and File No- BIO/MA/20/000103. This permission was given for restricted use in emergencies in the public interest as an abundant precaution in clinical trial mode. It means vaccines will be offered to restricted prioritized groups only. As you fell under this category, you have been invited to this plan. And Emergency Use Authorization (EUA). EUA declaration justifying emergency use of the products unless terminated or revoked (after which the products may no longer be used).

Conditions and Disqualifications for the Clinical Trials

Covaxin

Covaxin is an inactivated virus-based vaccine developed by Bharat Biotech, India. It requires two doses, with a gap of 4 to 6 weeks between them. Covaxin has been shown to have an efficacy rate of 77.8% in preventing symptomatic COVID-19 in a Phase 3 trial conducted in India.

For the clinical trial it was obligatory for the candidate to fulfill the following conditions under the 'restricted use of Covaxin, clinical trial mode 2021 provisions.

- 1- Consent for the vaccine
- 2- Age should be 18 years and above
- 3- Should be stable medical conditions. (Not requiring significant therapy, hospitalization, or worsening disease during the past three months.)

The candidate should be disqualified if they have the symptoms of having a fever, having a history of allergies, have a blood disorder, with any immunocompromised, pregnant women, breastfeeding mother, received any other Covid-19 vaccine, any other health-related issues declared by the vaccinator officer. After the clinical trial candidate may face some side effect and complications like fever, headache, malaise, weakness, vomiting, nausea,

rashes, body Ache, injection site itching, injection site pain, injection site redness, injection site swelling, weakness in injection arm, stiffness in the upper arm.

Chances of Severe Allergic Reaction (for which staying 30 min is compulsory)

Difficulty in breathing, fast heartbeat, tiredness and weakness, rash all over the body, swelling of face and throat.

Covishield is a viral vector vaccine developed by AstraZeneca and Oxford University, and is manufactured by Serum Institute of India. It requires two doses, with a gap of 4 to 12 weeks between them. Covishield has an efficacy rate of 70.4% in preventing symptomatic COVID-19 after the second dose, according to a Phase 3 trial conducted in the UK.

Sputnik-V is a viral vector vaccine developed by the Gamaleya Research Institute in Russia. It requires two doses, with a gap of 21 days between them. Sputnik-V has been shown to have an efficacy rate of 91.6% in preventing symptomatic COVID-19 in a Phase 3 trial conducted in Russia.

Corbevax is a protein subunit vaccine developed by the Indian pharmaceutical company Biological E. Limited. It requires two doses, with a gap of 28 days between them. Corbevax has completed Phase 2/3 clinical trials in India and is yet to receive regulatory approval.

Analysis

Covishield is an adenovirus vector-based vaccine. According to the 3rd phase of the clinical trial, the effectiveness of Covaxin is 80%, whereas the effectiveness of Covishield is about 90%. Covaxin, Covishield, Sputnik-V, and Corbevax are all effective COVID-19 vaccines with varying efficacy rates and storage requirements. The choice of the vaccine may depend on factors such as availability, cost, storage capacity, and population-specific requirements. It is important to note that getting vaccinated with any of these vaccines is crucial in controlling the spread of COVID-19 and reducing the risk of severe illness and death.

S.N.	Vaccine	Efficacy (%)	Storage Temp (°C)	Cost (Rs/Dose)	Age Coverage (Years)
1	Covaxin	78	2-8	295	18 to 60+
2	Covishield	90	3-6	225	12 to 60+
3	Sputnik-V	86	-18	995	8 to 60+
4	Corbevax	82	2-8	800	12 to 60+

(Das, 2022, 289, 297, 298, 299, 307) (Khan & Dhama, 2021, 2, 3) (Paradkar, 2022) (*Restricted Use of COVAXIN Under Clinical Trial Mode*, 2021) (Thiagarajan, 2022, 1) (Thuluva & Gunner, 2022, 7, 9, 10)

***Ph.D. Research Scholar**
Centre for Study in Science Policy
Jawaharlal Nehru University, Delhi-110067
 Email:- pradeepmaurya02@gmail.com

****Assistant Professor**
Centre for Study in Science Policy
Jawaharlal Nehru University, Delhi-110067
 Email:- anamikagulati@mail.jnu.ac.in

References

- Das, S. (2022, February 22). Immunogenic and reactogenic efficacy of Covaxin and Covishield. *Springer Science, Immunogenic Research (2022) 70:289-315*(Springer Science), 289, 297, 298, 299, 307. 10.1007/s12026-022-09265-0
- Khan, S., & Dhama, K. (2021, April 16). India's role in Covid-19 vaccine diplomacy. *Journal of travel medicine, 1-4*(Oxford University Press), 2, 3. 10.1093/jtm/taab064
- Paradkar, V. (2022, April 26). *Safety, tolerability and immunogenicity of Biological E's CORBEVAX™ vaccine in children and adolescents: A Prospective, Randomised, Double-blind, Placebo controlled, Phase-2/3 Study*. medRxiv. Retrieved September 7, 2022, from <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2022.04.20.22274076v1>
- *Restricted Use of COVAXIN Under Clinical Trial Mode*. (2021, January 11). MoHFW. Retrieved September 7, 2022, from <https://www.mohfw.gov.in/pdf/Version4PDFCOVAXINImplementationPlan11Jan2021.pdf>
- Thiagarajan, K. (2022, April 20). What do we know about India's Covaxin vaccine? *FEATURE, 373*(British Medical Journal (Online)), 1. 10.1136/bmj.n997
- Thuluva, S., & Gunner, S. R. (2022, September 3). Evaluation of safety and immunogenicity of receptor-binding domain-based COVID-19 vaccine (Corbevax) to select the optimum formulation in open-label, multicentre, and randomised phase-1/2 and phase-2 clinical trials. *eBio Medicine Articles, 83*(The Lancet),